

**THE STRUCTURE OF MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS. PART II.
THE MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF THE MOLECULAR
COMPOUNDS OF 2 : 4-DINITROPHENOL AND
2 : 4-DINITROCHLOROBENZENE WITH
HYDROCARBONS, PHENOLS
AND AMINES**

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Magnetic susceptibilities of the molecular compounds 2 : 4-dinitrophenol and 2 : 4-dinitrochlorobenzene with hydrocarbons phenols and amines have been measured and the results have been explained by taking into account the various resonance forms of the components in relation to the structure of molecular compounds.

In Part I (Shaney and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 335) we reported the magnetic susceptibilities of the molecular compounds of trinitrobenzene with hydrocarbons and phenols. Powell *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 153, 435) have shown that molecular compound formation between trinitrobenzene and *p*-iodoaniline is not due to the formation of any co-valent bond between the molecules. The view that the properties of these molecular compounds may be explained by assuming the formation of these through transfer of an electron from a hydrocarbon to the polynitro compound (Weiss, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 245) has not been supported by the study of their melting points and the intensities of X-ray including diffuse spectra (Powell, *ibid.*, 1943, 435).

We have expressed the view (Singh, *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) that the various resonance forms of the components play an important part in the formation of these complexes. We have extended this work to the molecular compounds of 2 : 4-dinitrophenol and 2 : 4-dinitrochlorobenzene with hydrocarbons, phenols and amines.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The molecular compounds were obtained by boiling alcoholic solutions of the components in molecular proportions. The compounds were repeatedly crystallised till their melting points agreed with those given in the literature.

Magnetic Susceptibility Determination

The magnetic susceptibility determinations of the substances were carried out on the modified form of Guoy's balance (Shaney and Singh, *loc. cit.*). Conductivity water with $\chi_M 0.72 \times 10^{-6}$ was taken as the reference substance. The apparatus was standardised by taking a number of observations on substances with known magnetic susceptibility values. The susceptibilities of the known substances with %error are given in Table I, those of the components and compounds in Table II, and the comparison of the magnetic susceptibilities of the molecular compounds with the additive sum of the χ_M of components, in Table III.

TABLE I

No.	Substance.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$		
		Exp.	Reported.	% Deviation.
1.	Potassium chloride	0.515	0.510	0.2
2.	Naphthalene	0.710	0.717	0.15
3.	Benzene	0.710	0.712	0.15
4.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol	0.395	0.397	0.30
5.	Ethyl alcohol	0.740	0.714	0.20

TABLE II

No.	Substance.	Mol. weight.	Expt. mean of 3 readings.	
			$\chi \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$ per g. mol.
1.	Naphthalene	128	0.708	91.9
2.	α -Naphthylamine	143	.690	86.67
3.	Benzidine	164	.626	115.18
4.	Aniline	93	.091	64.26
5.	α -Naphthol	144	.672	96.77
6.	β -Naphthol	144	.672	96.77
7.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol	184	.3935	72.31
8.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene	202	.418	84.44
9.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-naphthalene	312	.5455	170.35
10.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol- α -naphthylamine	327	.5323	173.96
11.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-benzidine.	368	.5265	194.67
12.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-aniline	277	.4632	133.79
13.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene-naphthalene	330	.5495	181.335
14.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- α -naphthol	346	.48104	166.426
15.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- β -naphthol	346	.55300	153.278
16.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene-aniline	285	.4804	141.6
17.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- α -naphthylamine.	345	.5501	193.20

TABLE III

No.	Compounds.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$ per g. mol.		Diff. between (1) and (2).
		Expt. (1)	Additive sum of components (2)	
1.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-naphthalene	170.35	164.215	- 6.136
2.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol- α -naphthylamine	173.964	170.982	- 2.982
3.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-benzidine	194.672	197.496	- 7.176
4.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol-aniline	133.791	136.576	+ 2.784
5.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene-naphthalene	181.335	170.340	- 4.996
6.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- α -naphthol	166.426	163.166	- 3.260
7.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- β -naphthol	153.278	181.204	+ 11.758
8.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene-aniline	141.6	181.204	+ 17.920
9.	2 : 4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene- α -naphthylamine	193.20	148.690	+ 7.697

DISCUSSION

Column 5 of Table III shows that the differences between the values of χ_{MAB} and the sum of χ_{MA} and χ_{MB} vary within a wide range and do not follow any sequence; they cannot therefore be due to any chemical linkage. Further, the differences are too big to be due to simple physical forces, such as weak Van der Waal's forces or the packing of the molecules.

These results, as shown in Part I (*loc cit.*), can be readily explained by taking into account the various resonance forms of the components.

Aniline can occur in the following resonance forms.

The mean of the above values is 64.25 which agrees closely with the experimental value of 64.35. The four resonance forms therefore contribute equally to the aniline molecule. The molecular compounds of aniline with 2:4-dinitrophenol and 2:4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene are less diamagnetic than the sum of χ_M of their components. It is probable that the molecular compound formation is due to the polarised forms of dinitro compounds with structures (I) and (IV) of aniline which would cause depression in the magnetic susceptibilities. The results of other compounds of 2:4-dinitrophenol and 2:4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene with hydrocarbons and amines can be similarly explained.

According to Briegleb (*Z. Physik*, 1932, 19, 255; 1934, 26, 63) the molecular complexes are the products of electrostatic interaction between the nitro group and the electric dipoles induced or already present in aromatic hydrocarbons and bases. The dipole aggregates can be set either side by side $\rightarrow\leftarrow$, or end to end $\rightarrow\rightarrow$. The permanent dipoles of the nitro group might be expected to interact according to the first mode of representation. It has been also suggested that the colour producing interactions such as take place between trinitrobenzene and naphthalene are of the end to end type and they may be regarded as the incipient oxidation-reduction processes. Only small differences between the experimental values can be expected if the phenomenon of the above type takes place. But as mentioned above, in many cases, the differences are quite large.

These results, as shown in Part J, can be readily explained by taking into account the various resonance forms of the components.

2 : 4-Dinitrophenol has the following structures due to the corresponding resonance of the nitro group between

and the ring ionisation.

The theoretical calculations for the different resonating forms have been made by Gray and Cruickshank's method as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The experimental value of χ_M 72.31 shows that the structures (II) and (III) predominate. Under proper conditions of activation, which are provided by the presence of the second anisotropic and polarisable component, there is an adjustment in the relative contributions of the different forms.

Let us take the case of 2 : 4-dinitrophenol-naphthalene complex. Naphthalene can occur in a number of forms (*loc. cit.*). The experimental value of χ_M 91.7×10^{-6} for naphthalene corresponds to the structures in which one of the rings is double bonded and the other ionic. The magnetic susceptibility of the above complex is greater than the sum of the components (*vide* Table III). This increase is due to the greater contribution of the polarised form (IV) of 2 : 4-dinitrophenol.

Again, let us take the case of aniline which can occur in the resonance forms as cited above. The mean of the above values is 64.25 which agrees closely with the experimental value of 64.35. The four resonance forms therefore contribute equally to the aniline molecule. The molecular compounds of aniline with 2 : 4-dinitrophenol and 2 : 4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene are less diamagnetic than the sum of χ_M of their components. It is obvious that the molecular compound formation is due to the polarised forms of dinitro compounds with structures (I) and (IV) of aniline which would cause depression in the magnetic susceptibilities.

This work is being continued.